

Fast, Good, and Cheap – You Can have all Three with Desktop 3D Scanning for Lithic Analysis

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Abstract

We report on our initial experience using a commercial desktop scanner to capture detailed 3D models of lithic flakes from Māori stone tool manufacture. Such models are useful for automating measurements of large flake collections, and offer the potential for more nuanced analysis through machine learning. The increasing availability and accuracy of consumer and prosumer grade equipment means that scan qualities that previously required expensive laser scanners are available on a more modest budget. Specifically, we use an EinScan SP scanner that retails for approximately NZ\$4,000, so is a similar price to a high-quality DSLR or mirrorless camera and lens kit.

While some experimentation is required to determine the optimal scan settings for a given application, once these are determined we find that it is a simple process to capture highly detailed scans with minimal manual intervention. Scanning takes 10-15 minutes per flake with the settings we found most effective, although there is potential to reduce this time. Visual comparison of the scans and original flakes indicates that fine surface details are captured reliably, although sharp edges can be smoothed slightly in the mesh-fitting process.

Keywords: 3D Scanning, Lithic Analysis

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Introduction

Digital 3D models of objects have found increasing use in archaeology and other related disciplines (e.g. Cerasoni et al. (2022), Göldner et al. (2022), Williams et al. (2024)). These models provide easier access to collections, including online; reduce handling of the original objects; and can form the basis for physical replicas via 3D printing. Many institutions are using these models for online catalogues, outreach, and communication. In these applications, high quality models of individual objects of interest are used to create compelling visualisations and allow for interactive exploration of the artefacts. With the growth of statistical shape analysis techniques, and machine learning in particular, there is a growing demand for high-volume scanning to produce large data sets for analysis.

One application where the issues of high-volume scanning arise is the analysis of lithic fragments. Waste flakes from the production of stone tools such as toki (adzes) form one of the most abundant sources of physical archaeological evidence in Aotearoa New Zealand, playing a similar role to ceramics in other parts of the world. There are large collections of these artefacts in museums, universities, and the production of a single tool may produce hundreds of flakes. Methods for creating 3D scans of these items would open avenues for automated analysis, but there is a common trade-off between cost, time, and quality in the scanning process.

Scanning Technologies

The two main options for desktop scanning of small artefacts have been photogrammetry and laser scanning. Both approaches can provide high quality models, but photogrammetry is low cost and time consuming while laser scanners are high cost but fast and easy to use. Recently, however, we have seen the introduction of relatively low-cost (NZ~\$4,000) desktop scanners that use a combination of photogrammetry and structured light. We believe that these devices have an interesting role in the trade-off of 'fast, good, and cheap' for the bulk scanning of small archaeological artefacts. A summary of the characteristics of photogrammetry, laser scanners, and the new range of desktop scanners is provided in Table 1.

Table 1 – Summary of common desktop scanning methods for small archaeological samples.

Method	Photogrammetry	Desktop Scanner	Laser Scanner
Price	Low (\$1,000 - \$4,000)	Low-Medium (\$4,000+)	High (\$20,000+)
Time	Varies (minutes -hours)	Low (minutes)	Low (minutes)
Quality	Varies (with time)	Good (~50 μ m)	High (~10 μ m)
Example	Canon R8 with 50mm lens	EinScan SP	3D Inspec

Photogrammetry uses multiple images of an object taken from different views of an object to recover its 3D shape. The process is essentially the same as stereo vision, except that we can use (many) more than two views of the world. The rapid development of digital camera

31 technology means that capturing such data sets is now easy. A mobile phone camera is more
32 than sufficient quality for photogrammetric reconstruction, although DSLR or mirrorless cam-
33 eras with fixed focal-length lenses are often used in order to give the best results. There are a
34 number of software packages that can process these images to produce 3D models, including
35 both free (e.g. COLMAP¹) and commercial (e.g. Agisoft Metashape², RealityCapture³) offerings.
36 While photogrammetry is low-cost and can give high quality models, it can be time consuming
37 to capture and process the images. Furthermore, the best results may require longer processing
38 times or manual masking of objects in images.

39 **Laser Scanners** measure the time-of-flight for a laser pulse to travel to and return from the
40 object in order to build an accurate 3D model. While they provide very high accuracy this technol-
41 ogy is generally expensive. ALthough low cost consumer devices using time-of-flight technology
42 do exist (e.g. Intel's I515 LiDAR camera⁴) they do not provide the accuracy needed for detailed
43 scanning of small samples. Desktop laser scanners often include a turntable to automatically
44 scan a whole object, providing an easy-to-use platform that provides high quality results, albeit
45 at a high cost.

46 **Desktop Scanners** such as the EinScan SP⁵ used in the project reported here are a relatively
47 recent development. Like desktop laser scanners they consist of a turntable and a sensor, but
48 different sensing technologies are used. In the case of the EinScan SP, the device has stereo
49 cameras and a projector that is used to superimpose structured light patterns on the object.
50 Structured light uses a known pattern of light to aid the photogrammetric 3D reconstruction
51 process in two main ways. Firstly, the use of structured light means that plain surfaces that
52 lack the texture detail needed for photogrammetry to align the images can be reconstructed.
53 Secondly, the curvature of the surface deforms the light pattern, and this can be used to infer
54 its shape.

55 Methods and Materials

56 Our initial sample of 30 lithic debitage flakes is from a stone working floor at the Wairau Bar
57 site at the north of the South Island of New Zealand, a source of adzes for trade around the coun-
58 try (Walter et al., 2010). This includes 11 flakes that we have used for previous analysis based on
59 photogrammetric analysis (Bennani et al., 2017). The flakes were scanned using an EinScan SP
60 desktop scanner and the associated (proprietary) EXScan software. The EinScan scanner uses
61 stereo cameras with structured light to capture multiple depth images of an object mounted on
62 an automated turntable, and can also be used on a tripod for larger objects.

63 Flakes were mounted vertically on the scanner as shown in Figure 1 (a) and two scans were
64 taken with a 180° rotation to ensure that both ends of the flake were captured (b). The two parts
65 are then stitched together within the software, and a watertight mesh fitted to create the final
66 model (c).

67 Some manual clean-up is often required before stitching the scans, in order to remove mount-
68 ing material that is often included in the scan. This process is generally fast and easy to do, since
69 it is generally acceptable to remove some of the scanned flake near the mounting material as

¹<https://colmap.github.io/>

²<https://www.agisoft.com/>

³<https://www.capturingreality.com/>

⁴<https://www.intelrealsense.com/lidar-camera-i515/>

⁵<https://www.einscan.com/einscan-sp/>

Figure 1 – Overview of the scanning process with the EinScan SP desktop scanner (a). Two or more 360° scans of the flake are made (b), ensuring that the entire surface is visible in at least one scan and there is good overlap. The mounting material is then manually removed; the two parts automatically stitched together, and a watertight mesh is fitted to the model (c)

70 long as there is sufficient overlap to allow the stitching of the two parts, and the entire flake is
 71 visible in at least one of the cleaned scans. In some cases, a third scan is necessary to capture
 72 the entire flake, this being taken with a half-rotation of the flake. Postprocessing tools within
 73 the EXScan software can also be used to sharpen or smooth the mesh, fill holes, etc., but were
 74 not applied in this study.

75

Results

76 The EXScan software allows the user to set a number of settings. We found that we needed
 77 to set quite long exposure times (due to the dark stone), and a small number of images was
 78 found to be most effective. It is possible to select how many images are taken in one revolution
 79 of the turntable and we found that 8 views gave the best results. This was somewhat surprising
 80 as we would have expected more images to lead to better quality scan. We found that using
 81 more images led to an increased rate of misalignment leading to the need to re-scan. The speed
 82 of the turntable can also be controlled, and we found the slowest setting was the best, so that
 83 the flakes do not move – firmer mounting could reduce this (and decrease scan time) but would
 84 require care not to damage the objects.

85 Using this approach we have scanned over 200 flakes from experimental archaeology assem-
 86 blages produced by Dante Bonica. The use of these modern assemblages means that we know
 87 the reduction sequence, and the materials do not have specific archaeological or cultural value.
 88 Through this process we found that we could reliably scan flakes down to approximately 20mm
 89 in size. An example scanned assemblage is shown in [Figure 2](#). The preform is approximately
 90 112mm long, 35mm wide, and 20mm thick. The largest individual flake is 60mm long, and the
 91 smallest 23mm in the longest axis.

92 Comparison with Photogrammetry

93 We also compare the results of the EinScan SP with desktop photogrammetry of a single flake.
 94 The photogrammetric model has 196,000 vertices and 329,000 faces, compared with 761,000
 95 vertices and 1,522,000 faces for the desktop scanner. This increase in detail is visible in the
 96 models, as shown in [Figure 3](#). The desktop scanner has recovered more of the fine surface detail
 97 and has sharper edges to the facets than the photogrammetric model.

98 Traditional photogrammetry can be time-consuming for individual flakes, and our earlier work
 99 on reconstructing multiple flakes in parallel gave much less detail (for one small flake, about

Figure 2 – Reconstruction of lithic fragments from a small assemblage. Small flakes < 20 mm and some larger but very thin flakes were not successfully scanned. The preform (top left) is approximately 112mm long.

Figure 3 – Reconstruction of a single flake using photogrammetry (left) and the desktop scanner (right).

100 27,000 points compared to 254,000). Visually the scans are more complete, and the EXScan
 101 software is able to automatically combine multiple scans at different orientations without the
 102 need for manual or approximate alignment approaches (Petrie et al., 2019).

103

Discussion

104 Our initial visual inspection of the scans indicates that there is a high level of detail captured
 105 by prosumer desktop scanners. The scanner produces metric data with 3D point locations in
 106 millimetres. We are currently preparing to measure the principle dimensions of the flakes in order
 107 to make a direct comparison with our earlier analysis using photogrammetry from consumer

108 camera images (Bennani, et al. 2017). These measurements can be made automatically, but the
109 scanned 3D models will first need to be oriented so that the flaking axis aligns with a fixed
110 co-ordinate axis.

111 Further work will investigate the use of machine learning to extract fine-grained shape fea-
112 tures and classify surface details such as automatically detecting the striking platform and flak-
113 ing axis direction. We also intend to develop a publicly available dataset of scanned flakes to
114 encourage further development of analysis tools, and provide a benchmark for comparison of
115 techniques. Based on our initial experiences, however, the scans that are produced capture fine
116 surface details well, and are suitable for further analysis. The ability to capture such high-fidelity
117 3D scans easily on comparatively inexpensive devices also opens many avenues for collection-
118 rather than object-scale analysis, and extending the utility of museum collections of such Māori
119 lithics for broader analytical studies.

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130 Conflict of interest disclosure

131 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of
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